
NEURONAL CRITICALITY AS A FRAMEWORK FOR THE COMPUTATIONAL NEUROPHENOMENOLOGY OF ADVANCED MEDITATION

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ABSTRACT

Here, we develop neuronal criticality as a framework for the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation. Epistemologically, neuronal criticality constrains the space of possible mapping functions between phenomenological and mathematical structures through empirical (and theoretical) results on variations of specific informational and dynamical properties with the distance to criticality. After introducing theoretical and neurophysiological connections between neuronal criticality and active inference, previous theoretical models and empirical findings on advanced meditation are contextualized in terms of the distance to criticality. Attentional control dynamics are proposed to endogenously self-regulate the distance to criticality in a task-relative manner. Several phenomenological characteristics of minimal phenomenal experience are shown to naturally emerge in a close-to-critical dynamical regime from the integrated framework. This includes, amongst others, increased *epistemic depth*; the phenomenology of *always already*; and the attenuation of the *first-person perspective* in terms of a particular computational feedback-loop (i.e., *epistemic ignition*). Indeed, mathematically, *more models of the modelling* process are situated within the computational regime near criticality. Furthermore, leveraging tools developed in the field of information geometry, we show how, in the

meditative endpoint of deconstruction called cessation of consciousness, the intrinsic Riemannian metric of the statistical manifold ‘collapses’ (i.e., becomes degenerate). The (in the limit) implied impossibility of belief-updating on that level is consistent with recent empirical results suggestive of critical dynamics during episodes of cessation. Neuronal criticality offers a promising framework for computational neurophenomenology, and the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation, and enables new families of empirical and theoretical constraints for further theorizing.

Keywords Neuronal criticality · Active inference · Minimal phenomenal experience · Advanced meditation

1 Introduction

Even though advanced states of meditation might have potentially wide-ranging implications for mental health and the development of insight, advanced meditation has only recently gained more scientific interest (Sacchet et al., 2024; Sezer and Sacchet, 2025; Sparby and Sacchet, 2024; Yang et al., 2024). In particular, recently, a number of models in the nascent field of computational neurophenomenology have been developed to account for the phenomenology of meditation and minimal phenomenal experience (MPE) (Metzinger, 2024; for a review of computational models of meditation, see (Tal et al., 2025)). These models have principally leveraged the active inference modeling framework (Da Costa et al., 2020; Friston et al., 2017), which is rooted in the free energy principle (Friston, 2010, 2019). Concretely, in the context of advanced meditation and MPE, these models attempt to capture phenomenological aspects such as attentional control, meta-awareness, equanimity, or the deconstruction of “the self”, in terms of functional variations of the information-theoretic composition of hierarchical generative models. Methodologically, computational neurophenomenology leverages these mathematical models as generative passages in bridging between the neuronal implementation and the associated phenomenological dynamics (Ramstead et al., 2022; Sandved-Smith et al., 2025). Historically, computational neurophenomenology can be seen as a computational extension of Varela’s neurophenomenological approach (Varela, 1996).

Here, neuronal criticality, and in particular, variations in the specific *distance to criticality*, will be developed as an alternative, yet complementary level of description for the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation. Because neuronal criticality is theoretically and

neurophysiologically connected with active inference, it is possible to contextualize previous empirical and theoretical work on advanced meditation in terms of the distance to criticality. Generally, neuronal criticality offers the epistemological advantage of significantly constraining the space of possible mappings between phenomenological and mathematical structures. This is possible by virtue of the accumulated research findings over the last decade on neuronal criticality that have characterized variations in numerous dynamical and informational properties with the distance to criticality. Often, some of these dynamical and informational properties are, due to their genericity and diversity, mathematically related to a given structure functioning as a formal model of an aspect of experience. Therefore, systematic variations of these structures with the distance to criticality enable extrapolations of how phenomenological properties *would* have to transform (as the distance to criticality is altered in a given class of states (e.g., various sleep stages, psychoactive substances, etc.; for a review see (Gervais et al., 2023)) *if* a given phenomenological-computational mapping were adequate. In this sense, neuronal criticality promises new families of empirical and theoretical constraints for computational neurophenomenology.

2 From the critical brain hypothesis to dynamic adaptive computation

The critical brain hypothesis is the idea that large-scale neuronal dynamics are posed at, or near, the boundary of a critical phase transition (for reviews see Beggs and Timme, 2012; Cocchi et al., 2017; O’Byrne and Jerbi, 2022; Tian et al., 2022; Wilting and Priesemann, 2019; for a recent book see Beggs, 2022). Avalanche criticality is the most common type of criticality in the neuroscience literature; being sometimes also called ‘crackling noise’ (Sethna et al., 2001), or ‘the edge of activity propagation’ (Muñoz, 2018). Here, the two separated phases themselves can be seen in terms of the average number of active postsynaptic neurons following the activity of a given presynaptic neuron (this perspective on criticality is known as the branching model (Jensen, 1998; Miranda and Herrmann, 1991; Pruessner, 2012). Intuitively, if this branching parameter, m , is below 1, activity, A , exponentially recedes over time (h denotes external input). On the other hand, if m is above 1, activity exponentially increases.

$$\langle A_{t+1} | A_t \rangle = mA_t + h\Delta t$$

$$\tau = -\frac{\Delta t}{\ln(m)}$$

The branching parameter is associated with the intrinsic timescale of the neuronal dynamics: As m increases towards 1 from below, approaching the critical state – and every neuronal event comes on average closer to causing one other neuronal event – the intrinsic timescale increases ever further (theoretically, diverges to infinity), as the activity reverberates ever-longer in the network (e.g., Wilting & Priesemann, 2019). This increase in the intrinsic timescale is known as critical slowing down (Scheffer et al., 2012). Because at this critical point, $m = 1$, activity neither recedes nor explodes, neuronal avalanches (i.e., chains of neuronal activation) come in all sizes (i.e., they are scale-free or scale-invariant). The slope of this power law distribution over avalanche sizes is expected to be 1.5 for critical branching processes (Pruessner, 2012), and corresponding power law distributions of avalanche sizes were found in many experiments. After the original study by (Beggs and Plenz, 2003) which found power law distributed avalanches in the LFPs of cultured slices, subsequent studies *in vitro* revealed similar distributions in LFPs and spiking activity of cultured dissociated neurons and cortical slices (Mazzoni et al., 2007; Pasquale et al., 2008; Tetzlaff et al., 2010). Power laws have also been reported in MEG (Shriki et al., 2013), EEG (Jannesari et al., 2020; Linkenkaer-Hansen et al., 2001) and in fMRI (Fraiman et al., 2009; Tagliazucchi et al., 2012), as well as in calcium and voltage imaging (Bellay et al., 2015; Ponce-Alvarez et al., 2018), and in LFPs from intracranial depth electrodes (Priesemann et al., 2013).

However, it has been argued that coarse measures could sample from overlapping populations, and that this may lead to the (false) detection of power laws, given the enhanced correlation between measurement sites (Neto et al., 2022). Consistently with this concern, many more fine-grained studies of *in vivo* spiking activity often differ from power laws, revealing slightly subcritical neuronal dynamics instead (for a review see Wilting and Priesemann, 2019). Furthermore, a number of noncritical processes also lead to power laws (Priesemann and Shriki, 2018; Touboul and Destexhe, 2010) and power law analyses are inherently ambiguous, requiring a choice of the bin size and threshold. A recently developed subsampling invariant estimator (Spitzner et al., 2021) also revealed a slightly subcritical, reverberating regime ($0.94 < m < 0.995$) (Wilting et al., 2018). Accordingly, and consistent with the systematic problems of power law analyses – which may, especially on coarse recording modalities, falsely infer a close proximity to criticality by virtue of measurement artifacts – accumulating evidence from *in vivo* spiking activity reveals the brain as poised in a slightly subcritical dynamical regime, adding nuance to the original critical brain hypothesis.

However, a crucial point that distinguishes self-organized criticality from the more conventional criticality in statistical physics is that in self-organized criticality, systems tune themselves to criticality, without the need for external tuning via a control parameter. In a self-organized critical

system, the critical point is an attractor, meaning the system tends to evolve toward that point from a wide range of starting points. For a review on long term and short term-plasticity rules that tune and sustain neural networks near the critical regime, see (Zeraati et al., 2021). Nevertheless – as reviewed above – the evidence is mixed, indicating that the brain might not self-organize itself towards the critical point per se, but rather towards a slightly-subcritical reverberating regime.

Different distances to the critical point are associated with a number of variations in computational properties. The framework of dynamic adaptive computation (Wilting et al., 2018) posits that the brain self-regulates neuronal dynamics to varying distances to criticality, based on currently experienced task-demands and context – thereby, that is, by virtue of modifying macroscale computational properties, effectively instating a form of meta-optimization. For instance, a closer distance to the critical state makes the system maximally sensitive to perturbations, a phenomenon known as divergent susceptibility (Binney et al., 1992). Relatedly, the dynamic range – the range of inputs the network is able to differentially respond to – is maximized at criticality (Kinouchi and Copelli, 2006). Criticality has also been shown to maximize the number of metastable states (Haldeman and Beggs, 2005), afford rich input-output mappings (Maass et al., 2002), and create an optimal balance of integration and segregation (Timme et al., 2016). Furthermore, the scale-invariant nature of neuronal avalanches creates long range correlations in space and time – thereby effectively nullifying the path length between nodes through the network and over time (O’Byrne and Jerbi, 2022).

Information-theoretically, furthermore, criticality is closely associated with a maximized information transmission, and capacity. Greenfield and Lécarré already showed in 2001 that the mutual information between different neurons in a model of a neural network peaks at criticality (Greenfield and Lécarré, 2001), mirroring earlier work on cellular automata that demonstrated a maximized mutual information between cells at criticality (Li et al., 1990). By systematically changing the excitation-inhibition ratio in a network model and in *in vitro* cortex cultures, (Shew et al., 2011) similarly discovered that both information capacity (i.e., Shannon entropy) and information transmission (i.e., mutual information) are maximized at that particular value of the excitation-inhibition ratio at which power law distributed neuronal avalanches emerge. This increased information capacity is consistent with earlier work by (Stewart and Plenz, 2006) who varied dopamine tone in cortex slices, revealing that a broadened diversity of activity patterns co-emerged with critical signatures. Furthermore, (Fagerholm et al., 2016) – concerned with the limited spatial coverage and resolution of previous experimental techniques, and overcoming them by using genetically encoded voltage imaging in layer 2/3 pyramidal cells from mice cortex with $< 100 \mu\text{m}$ spatial resolution – found that, as mice recovered from anaesthesia, cortical mutual information and Shannon entropy increased.

This increase in information capacity and transmission (as well as region-specific variability) was accounted for by the extent to which the dynamics became scale-free (i.e., critical). Conversely, learning and synaptic plasticity rules which optimize mutual information result in networks that evince signatures of criticality (Tanaka et al., 2009)). As might be expected, it has been argued that evolution may have selected critical dynamics for the advantageous information-processing capabilities it confers (Hidalgo et al., 2014).

However, criticality also maximizes further aspects, which are likely negative for function in some contexts. For example, the variability of network responses diverges, entailing a reduced specificity (Gollo, 2017) and reliability (Wilting et al., 2018). Furthermore, supercriticality is associated with instability (Priesemann et al., 2014) and critical slowing down results in a significant delay before a response, which is non-adaptive in tasks in which a fast action is required. Similarly, a high dynamic range may result in an increased interference from non-task-specific inputs. These examples highlight that many of the properties that were – under some circumstances and tasks – computationally adaptive, also have task and context dependent negative consequences. Indeed, instead of maximizing particular computational properties, a context and task-specific *sufficient* expression of a given property is more ecologically plausible (Wilting and Priesemann, 2019). For instance, networks vary the distance to the critical point in balancing specificity and sensitivity (Gollo, 2017) or representational detail and integration time (Shriki and Yellin, 2016). Essentially, because of the functional relationship between m and associated properties of criticality, where small changes in m correspond to large changes in, for example, the neuronal timescale or the network sensitivity, it has been proposed that neuronal networks may actively and adaptively control m , thereby inducing significant task- and context-dependent changes in the timescale and associated computational properties of global neuronal population dynamics (Wilting et al., 2018; Wilting and Priesemann, 2019).

But how long does it take for the brain to dynamically self-regulate the distance to criticality? Some experiments evidence a self-regulation over several hours. For instance, after monocular deprivation was used to cause a large distance to criticality in the rodent V1, neuronal dynamics restored critical dynamics after about 48 hours despite ongoing monocular deprivation (Ma et al., 2019). Other experiments, however, also provide evidence of self-regulation over very short periods. For instance, the presentation of a visual stimulus briefly disrupted critical dynamics in the visual cortex of a turtle, but critical dynamics were restored within 2-5 seconds, even though visual stimulation continued (Clawson 2017; see also Shew 2015).

Given this drastic difference in the timescales of regulation, distinct neurophysiological mechanisms seem plausible. And indeed, diverse mechanisms, such as Hebbian rules (de Arcangelis and Herrmann, 2010; de Arcangelis et al., 2006; Effenberger et al., 2015; Meisel and Gross, 2009) or homeostatic plasticity (for a review see (Zeraati et al., 2021)) present a range of the possible options. Furthermore, recently, and conceptually aligned with the general-purpose adaptivity of being able to control the dynamical regime on comparatively short time-scales, it has been proposed that the different arms of the ascending arousal system conjointly instantiate a heterogeneous set of control parameters for criticality (Mueller et al., 2025; Shine, 2023). From this perspective, macroscopic properties of global neuronal population dynamics across the cortex and connected subcortical structures could, in a non-monotonic and circuit dependent manner, and by virtue of modulating the excitability of target sites, be controlled through neuromodulators such as dopamine, acetylcholine or noradrenaline, released from the ascending arousal system. The broad though heterogeneous coverage over target sites, the comparatively low-dimensional nature of the control-system (affording ‘steerability’), and the induced modulation of effective gain, situate the ascending arousal system as particularly well-poised to regulate the distance to criticality on comparatively short time-scales. In this way, phasic neuromodulatory bursts provide rapid transient steering around tonic set-points (Mueller et al., 2025; Shine, 2023). Indeed, from this perspective, closed-loop task- and context-dependent control of the distance to criticality can be enabled by virtue of descending connections from cortex to distinct brainstem and forebrain nuclei forming part of the ascending arousal system.

3 Prediction, precision and the distance to criticality

Recent developments in theoretical neuroscience have prompted a shift in cognitive neuroscience: away from conceiving the brain as a passive sensory filter and toward viewing it as a statistical organ that generates hypotheses that are continually tested by, and constrained against, sensory evidence (Clark, 2013, 2015; Friston et al., 2017; Hohwy, 2013). This outlook traces back to Helmholtz’s notion of unconscious inference (Helmholtz, 1962) and contemporary renditions of Helmholtz’s idea are now among the leading candidates for a neuronally instantiated mechanics of beliefs. A considerable amount of anatomical and physiological evidence supports predictive coding (Adams et al., 2013; Bastos et al., 2012; Friston, 2008; Mumford, 1992; Shipp et al., 2013). Under this theory, and situated in a functional hierarchy, (relatively) higher cortical levels generate predictions about (relatively) lower-level events. These predictions are compared against lower-level activity to yield prediction errors (often associated with superficial pyramidal cells).

The resulting mismatch signals are propagated back up the hierarchy to the next instantiation of this process, updating higher-level representations (with predictions being often associated with deep pyramidal cells). In this sense, ascending prediction errors can be regarded as broadcasting the ‘newsworthy’ information not yet captured by descending predictions (Kanai et al., 2015). However, the brain must select which channels to prioritize by adjusting the gain of prediction errors that compete to influence higher-level expectations. In Bayesian terms, this gain corresponds to the precision (inverse variance) assigned to ascending prediction errors, analogous to weighting effects by their standard errors in statistics (Kanai et al., 2015). Due to these properties, precision has been associated with attention, with top-down attentional control amounting to precision-deployment ((Feldman and Friston, 2010); for a review see (Limanowski et al., 2024)). More specifically, the precision of action policies has been linked to the dopaminergic system (FitzGerald et al., 2015), the noradrenergic system has been related to a “global model failure” (potentially associated with the precision in transition probabilities) (Jordan, 2024; Sales et al., 2019), and the cholinergic system may correspond to the top-down control of selective attention (i.e., modulating likelihood precision) (Moran et al., 2013). For a recent study using pharmacological manipulations of all three neuromodulators in line with this perspective see (Marshall et al., 2016). This implementation also foregrounds the excitation–inhibition balance as a key mediator of precision-weighted message passing (Humphries et al., 2009).

Notably, there is significant overlap between control parameters of criticality and implementations of precision. The effective recurrent activation, m , can be implemented by a number of physiological mechanisms, including an increased excitation-inhibition ratio, altered synaptic strength, or even dendritic processing (for a proposal of error computations in predictive coding centred on dendrites, see (Mikulasch et al., 2023) (Wilting et al., 2018)). While it deserves to be mentioned that potential mechanisms are not mutually exclusive, the potentially most direct relationship to implementations of precision is constituted by neuromodulation (see section 2), being engendered by the ascending arousal system as a heterogeneous, global, and comparatively short-timescale mechanism by which the distance to criticality can be flexibly modulated in a task-dependent and region-relative manner (Mueller et al., 2025; Shine, 2023). From this perspective, top-down precision deployment emerges as a functionally and anatomically plausible control mechanism of the distance to criticality that explains how the distance to criticality is endogenously altered across experiential states, modes, tasks, and even in the absence of alterations in sensory input.

A common denominator of many current computational models of advanced meditation concerns an increase of the variance of hierarchically high-level beliefs (as facilitated by endogenous precision-deployment down-regulating the associated likelihood precision; for a review of computational

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models of meditation, see (Tal et al., 2025)). Phenomenologically, this maps onto reduced conceptual and self-relational processing, and onto a stronger focus on current sensory inputs by virtue of the relatively increased influence of bottom-up information flow. This induction of a higher variance of hierarchically high-level beliefs offers a complementary mathematical perspective to how neuronal criticality interrelates with the predictive machinery instantiated by the brain. Specifically, an ever higher-variance of (high-level) beliefs – corresponding, in a free-energy minimization scheme, to an increased emphasis on the minimization of complexity (relative to the maximization of accuracy) – mathematically implies longer relaxation times (Friston et al., 2012). This increased relative emphasis on the minimization of complexity is consistent with phenomenological descriptions of meditation in terms of a maximally simple state ((Metzinger, 2024); also see section 3). In statistical physics, critical slowing down, as mentioned in section 2 in the context of the branching model, is a generic feature of continuous (second-order) phase transitions. Thus – and while critical slowing down underdetermines the *particular* underlying phase transition – the presence of increased relaxation times, being induced by one of the most central computational mechanisms descriptive of the phenomenology of meditation, suggests that neuronal population dynamics are situated near some continuous phase transition. Notably, and given the existence of numerous differences and similarities between psychedelics and meditation, this mathematical relationship has already been leveraged by the REBUS model in modeling the psychedelic state (Carhart-Harris and Friston, 2019).

4 Neuronal criticality as a framework for advanced meditation

Simply mapping numerous distinct practices of meditation to a closer distance to criticality is too coarse-grained in order to exhaustively account for nuanced changes across various forms of practice and levels of expertise. Indeed, and as reviewed in section 2, a closer distance to criticality introduces a genuine *tradeoff* between computational properties advantageous and disadvantageous for a given task and context. While there are numerous properties of criticality which are advantageous for some forms of practice, and closely aligned with the respective phenomenology (see below), one example of a non-adaptive property in the context of one particular meditative practice – i.e., focused awareness meditation – consists of a decreased response reliability near criticality. Indeed, phenomenologically, a high response reliability is one of the central necessary functionalities that is characteristically implied by concentration meditation. Response reliability is increased further away from the critical state (in the subcritical regime) (e.g., Gollo, 2017; see also O’Byrne and Jerbi, 2022); with neuronal dynamics being, effectively – due to the fewer degrees of freedom compared to

the more entropic critical state – adaptively confined to a lower-dimensional subspace. Consistently, empirically, it has been found that long-range temporal correlations (measured via EEG) decrease in focused awareness practices, which has been interpreted as evidence of subcriticality, as compared to the resting state (Irrmischer et al., 2018; Pascarella et al., 2025; Walter and Hinterberger, 2022). Indeed, these findings may also be interpreted in terms of the specific intentional and goal-directed aspects of these practices, which induce – compared to other practices and modes of experience – a subset of comparatively precise high-level expectations (mapping onto a larger distance to criticality) regarding what “successful” concentration meditation consists of. Phenomenologically, this maps onto the experience of striving and the “in-order-to” mindset (consistent with the relationship between the distance to criticality and the relative influence of epistemic and pragmatic self-models, see below). Accordingly, and at the risk of being redundant, the distance to criticality is regulated relative to the specific mixture of advantageous and non-advantageous computational properties for a given task: Given that meditation comprises diverse practices, different distances to criticality are to be expected. Indeed, it is precisely this expressivity that makes neuronal criticality well-posed as a *framework* for the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation.

In contrast, in another meditative practice — open-monitoring meditation — the attentional field is not concentrated on a small region of experiential space but rather distributed more evenly across and within sensory modalities. Given this desideratum of an extended attentional field, it might be expected that this practice benefits from a closer distance to criticality due to the increased information integration that this dynamical regime affords (see section 2). Indeed, various higher-order information atoms (e.g., synergy or redundancy) can only exist in the presence of multiple sources and have been shown to increase near criticality (e.g., (Cramer et al., 2020)), consistent with the general increase in information capacity and transmission (for a study demonstrating increased synergy during (Rajyoga) meditation, see (Kumar et al., 2024); see also (Luppi et al., 2021)). Furthermore, the increased dynamic range (i.e., the increased range of input strengths over which the system can transmit information effectively) obtained near criticality may be interpreted in terms of flexible precision-deployment across widely different intensity levels (i.e., allocating attention to the degree necessary for ‘noticing’ the given, potentially very subtle, stimulus). Consistently, it has been found empirically that the distance to criticality is reduced in open-monitoring meditation (Pascarella et al., 2025).

As reviewed in section 2, the information capacity of neuronal population dynamics increases near the critical point. The entropic brain hypothesis (Carhart-Harris, 2018; Carhart-Harris et al., 2014) describes this information-theoretic entropy as corresponding to the “richness” of conscious content – intuitively understandable in terms of a larger phenomenological diversity mapping

onto a higher entropy. While the entropic brain hypothesis was originally formulated in the context of psychedelics, the general argument of an increased entropy that is phenomenologically descriptive has recently been leveraged in the context of advanced meditation and computational phenomenology – describing a process of hierarchical deconstruction that induces less-constrained systemic-dynamics evincing a larger repertoire of possible states (Mago et al., 2024).

Indeed, the often described *profundity* and *incommunicability* of deep meditative experiences (Metzinger, 2024) may be understood in terms of a comparatively reduced information transmission facilitated by more abstract conceptual-linguistic ‘system-2’ access and processing, which – while being insufficient to account for fine-grained phenomenological distinctions generally (mapping onto the phenomenology of *ineffability* (Ji et al., 2024)) – would be expected to be even more dwarfed in relation to the increased information capacity of neuronal dynamics near criticality. Empirically, consistently, neuronal dynamics underlying meditative states have been shown to be characterized by a higher entropy (as well as other measures of complexity; for a review (Atad et al., 2025)).

Intriguingly, and as noted by (Carhart-Harris and Friston, 2019), the attenuation of the precision of (hierarchically high-level) beliefs can be interpreted in terms of a flattened free-energy landscape, which, in turn, precisely due to this flattening, maps onto increased relaxation times (and can be interpreted in terms of critical slowing) (see section 2 and 3). The increasingly flattened generative conditional likelihood of those beliefs (enabled in some forms of meditation by virtue of precision-deployment and inducing flattened posteriors) implies a minimization of inferential complexity (a minimized divergence between prior and posterior). This in turn implicitly encodes a form of regularization, favouring parsimonious, perturbation-robust inferences that increasingly generalize across contexts. Indeed, analogously in machine learning, many training schemes of artificial neural networks explicitly or implicitly search for flat basins (Chaudhari et al., 2017; Keskar et al., 2017). This is consistent with theoretical generalization bounds drawing on the notion of (invariantly measurable) curvature (Tsuzuku et al., 2020), and PAC-Bayesian statements leveraging a divergence directly (McAllester, 1998). Phenomenologically, consistently, MPE has been described as maximally simple and minimally fabricated. Put in the words of (Metzinger, 2024): “[...] there clearly is a distinct phenomenal character of awareness itself, and for now, it does remain the prime candidate for the simplest and subtlest form of conscious experience that human beings are capable of.” Indeed, it is precisely this ‘simplification’ of high-level beliefs that induces a generalized sensitivity to the environment (and higher neuronal complexity measures (see above)).

Interestingly, some advanced meditators seem to have a strong pre-theoretical intuition – as opposed to having inhabited a very specific, constrained region of phenomenal state-space, the resulting inference based of which might be limited precisely because these states are so unusual – that certain properties of the nature of mind have, in fact, *always already* been the case (for the phenomenology of *always already*, and the related notion of the *most natural state*, see Metzinger, 2024). It is possible that some advanced states of meditation facilitate the meta-cognitive inference of the very fact that systemic dynamics are (or, have been) situated in increasingly flattened variational free energy basins: From this perspective, the phenomenology of *always already* describes inferences that have generalized in the past, and are expected to generalize in the future. Strikingly, consciousness, deconstructed to its minimally sufficient instantiation that is MPE, “looks as if” it would generalize.

Neuronal dynamics situated near criticality, imply, on the computational level of description, the potential for an increased epistemic affordance available for (attentional) action selection (formally, the larger Shannon entropy of beliefs implies the potential for a larger epistemic value (which is resultant from a particular decomposition of the expected free energy (Friston et al., 2015))), as, intuitively, (attentional) actions can only be genuinely epistemic when there is uncertainty to be resolved. This mirrors the phenomenology of an increased *epistemicity* characterizing some advanced states of meditation (Metzinger, 2024). The phenomenological duality of exploration and exploitation is manifest in active inference in terms of epistemic and pragmatic value (jointly constituting the expected free energy (e.g., see Parr et al., 2022)). One hyperparameter that determines the balance of epistemic and pragmatic value in action selection is the precision of the prior preference distribution (with prior preferences determining the phenotypically expected ‘goal-state’ of the system).

Seen from another perspective: The belief that “I am a cause in the world, or an agent” (Hohwy and Michael, 2017)), is equivalent to the belief that “I act to maintain myself in certain states” (Hohwy and Michael, 2017), being constituted by the hierarchically highest (i.e., maximally invariant) inference corresponding to the prior preferences. Prior preferences have to be invariant, (Friston, 2011, page 2) writes: “This is easy to see by considering the alternative: If the agent (model) entailed prior expectations that it will change irreversibly, then (as an optimal model of itself), it will cease to exist in its present state. Therefore, if the agent (model) exists, it must a priori expect to occupy an invariant set of bounded states (cf., homeostasis)”. Due to their high systemic invariance, prior preferences have been closely tied to self-modelling, especially to the (weak) first person perspective and minimal self-modelling. Minimal self-modelling is the simplest form of self-consciousness and has been formulated (originally) in terms of the three necessary and sufficient conditions of (1) a global transparent self-identification with the body as a whole, (2) spatiotemporal

self-location, and (3) a (weak) first-person perspective (Blanke and Metzinger, 2009). The (weak) first person perspective is a purely geometric anchor that corresponds to the centre of projection of the embodied system, functionally understood in terms of a maximum dynamical invariance (Metzinger, 2013). In active inference, this maps onto the prior preference distribution, which, for a given free-energy minimizing system, isomorphically specify its particular instantiation.

In deep states of meditation, and consistent with neuronal dynamics being situated in the close vicinity of criticality (mapping onto generally flattened beliefs), it is precisely the flattening of the preference distribution that makes the preferences (by definition) less invariant – inducing both a (degree of) dissolution of the (weak) first person perspective, and a higher emphasis on epistemic versus pragmatic value by virtue of an automatically ensuing hyperparameter-tuning. Put in relation to the phenomenological contraction principle (Metzinger, 2020) – which describes self-modelling as implying a *felt contraction* of the representational space – the comparatively lower precision of prior preferences opens the possibility for action-selection to expand over a broadened (i.e., less contracted) posterior over policies. This is consistent with the meditative phenomenology of generally reduced *tension* and *grasping* (Prest and Berryman, 2024). Indeed, a decreased precision of the prior preference distribution, specifically, has been proposed to map onto meditation-induced *equanimity* (Sandved-Smith, 2024).

While exclusively epistemic actions may turn out to be a coarse-grained idealization of the underlying exploration-exploitation balance, strongly epistemic (attentional) actions target those observations that are predicted to yield the highest epistemic gain, effectively independently of prior preferences: However, while observations that yield a high epistemic gain are, on average, and at a given time, effectively unrelated to prior preferences, preferences are updated by those epistemic (i.e., often, diverse) observations: The psychological mere-exposure effect describes the tendency of human beings to prefer outcomes they are familiar with; having been investigated across over 400 studies (for a review see Bornstein and Craver-Lemley, 2022). Whether seen in terms of an increased processing fluency afforded by familiarity, a relatedly improved resource-efficiency, or in terms of general tendencies of risk-aversion and functional asymmetries in valence processing (i.e., ‘that which is known to be safe, tends to be safe, so, given that “bad is stronger than good” (Baumeister et al., 2001), familiar observations will be preferred’), this general tendency describes the updating of preferences as a function of knowledge in the direction of ‘liking what you know’.

While (attentional) prior preferences are (by definition) constrained onto a particular set of observations, and in part (due to their centrality for the system) very unlikely to update into entirely different regimes (with evolutionarily in-built constraints being likely), it is precisely by virtue of

facilitating (usually) diverse observations that a high epistemic value characterizing (attentional) action selection is expected to reduce extrinsic value contrasts encoded by the (second-order) prior preference distribution. This can be modeled using preference learning (learning prior preferences via Dirichlet updates ((e.g., Sajid et al., 2021); see the mathematical Appendix for details on this inference scheme)).

However – because of this attenuation of extrinsic value contrasts – this, in turn, tilts action selection further towards the epistemic side, effectively inducing a dynamical feed-back loop (i.e., *epistemic ignition*) that instantiates a form of self-evidencing on the level of types of self-modeling (*expansive* vs. *contractive*) which recursively tunes systemic dynamics closer to criticality (as, generally, flattened beliefs facilitate a smaller distance to criticality (see section 3)).

This increased epistemicity in attentional action selection, characterizing advanced meditation, is also consistent with the more precise second-order likelihood (see below), which has been mapped to the phenomenological presence of *meta-awareness* (Sandved-Smith et al., 2021): A more precise (second-order) likelihood formally yields, on average, a larger epistemic value (by virtue of implying the potential for a larger reduction in uncertainty (see the Appendix)). Furthermore, this endogenously driven auto-epistemic feedback loop, which, under usual circumstances, is held in check by contractive (i.e., pragmatic) self-model type self-evidencing (i.e., preference learning in the context of preferences as observations) could reach an initial ‘escape velocity’ by virtue of top-down precision deployment initially increasing the temperature of prior preferences.

Intriguingly, therefore, this perspective might offer the computational solution to an (apparent) conceptual (and experiential) problem: “You can’t get rid of your hallucination of being an ego by an activity of the ego” (Watts, 1972), as – even though the attentional inspection of an n -th order inference, recursively directed at the process of construction of the $n-1$ th order-layer might very well opacify the transparency that was necessary for the genuine identification with a (minimal) self-model on the $n-1$ th level – it is the very presence of that higher-order layer effecting this process that *itself* presupposes a transparent self-model, anchored on (n -th order meta-) attentional preferences. Expressed in the words of (Friston et al., 2012): “I can never conceive of what it is like to be me, because that would require the number of recursions I can physically entertain, plus one.” And, indeed, in generic variational free energy minimization schemes, the number of hierarchically stacked meta-attentional layers is heavily constrained due to the minimization of complexity.

However, by virtue of this endogenous epistemic feed-back loop (i.e., *epistemic ignition*), genuine epistemic attentional practices are expected to gradually anneal the precision of prior preferences, thereby attenuating the very functional invariance postulated as the dynamical correspondent

of the (weak) first person perspective understood as strictly necessary for minimal phenomenal self-modeling. Put simply, it is possible for minimal self-models to cease entirely in advanced meditation, not by intentional transcendence, but by an *auto-epistemically induced dissolution* – with neuronal population dynamics near criticality effectively encoding an ignition of epistemicity that de-contracts the phenomenal unit of identification onto *awareness as such*.

Furthermore, and relative to the second mechanism referenced above of an increased (second order) likelihood precision inducing a larger epistemic value in attentional action selection (by virtue of offering an increased information transmission (see the Appendix)), the decreased likelihood precision of first-order states maps onto a reduced first order epistemic value. Simultaneously occurring with the flattened (first-order) preferences, this is consistent with the meditative proficiency reached by the *absence* of (first-order) action, and the phenomenology of *stillness*.

Simultaneously, and again, consistently, the attenuated variance of prior preferences in some advanced states of meditation, and in the vicinity of criticality, induces – seen in the light of the self-simulational theory of temporal extension (Bellingrath, 2023) – a smaller extension of the “felt length” of the present moment, thereby being consistent with phenomenological reports of alterations of temporal experience in MPE ((Metzinger, 2024); for a computer simulation of a deep parametric generative model showing these effects in the context of advanced meditation, see (Bellingrath, 2024)).

5 The information geometry of minimal phenomenal experience and cessations in the vicinity of neuronal criticality

Generative conditional distributions are mathematically situated in a statistical manifold (the space of possible distributions), which is equipped with a Riemannian metric (the Fisher information tensor; for a general introduction to information geometry, see (Amari, 2016)). Intuitively – as opposed to the familiar Euclidean metric, where small standardized movements in one particular direction induce a fixed amount of change – this intrinsic metric of the statistical manifold measures the sensitivity of the induced probability distribution to changes in the parameters; with a large Fisher information thereby inducing a higher traversed distance in the statistical manifold, and vice versa. Strikingly, while the particular coordinates within which we seek to express a particular distribution are reparameterizable, and in this sense inherently observer-laden and arbitrary, the Fisher information tensor as a metric of the statistical manifold is *intrinsic* to the manifold, (i.e., reparameterization-invariant).

Some advanced states of meditation have been characterized in terms of a high-precision weighting of second-order attentional states (i.e., their process of construction), set by hierarchically higher states (Sandved-Smith et al., 2021). Indeed, this functionally enables faster and more reliable inferences on the second-order level, and has been understood phenomenologically in terms of the presence of *meta-awareness*, which is expected to be increased in meditative practice (Sandved-Smith et al., 2021). In relation to neuronal criticality, as described above, second-order attentional policies (or habits) which induce a larger variance of (hierarchically high-level) first-order beliefs, entail a smaller distance to criticality (see section 3)). Generally, small variations in the control parameter for criticality modify large-scale computational and dynamical properties of neuronal population dynamics (effectively a form of meta-optimization; see section 2). Given the various thus induced adaptive and non-adaptive properties for a given task and context, as well as general dangers near criticality, such as the possibility of tipping over into epilepsy (Cerf et al., 2004; Zimmern, 2020), functionally very fine-grained control of the distance to criticality is a necessity. Generally, and across many systems in statistical physics, overall systemic dynamics are uniquely sensitively coupled to the control parameter surrounding the critical regime. Here, this sensitivity effectively induces the demand for precise, fast, and reliable (second order) inference and control. Accordingly – next to the phenomenological and inferential plausibility of a high-likelihood precision of second-order attentional states (mapping onto meta-awareness) – this specific computational regime is uniquely equipped with the possibility for scaffolding second-order inferences that enable fast and reliable control of the distance to criticality.

Interestingly, the functional necessity of this high-precision weighting makes it possible to mathematically infer that more meta-cognitively distinguishable *models of the modelling* process are situated in the computational regime in the vicinity of criticality. Generally, conceptually, two phenomenal contents appear experientially as *identical*, when no difference-relata are available to distinguish them. More precisely, these ‘identity criteria’ are not intended to be understood to reside on the conceptual level (in this context, see Metzinger, 2003) in the sense of necessary and sufficient identity criteria for individual classes of phenomenal content, but rather in terms of generic informational difference-relations, functionally available for further (meta-cognitive) inference, and instantiated relative to the representational grain of the respective system. Given that in the dynamical regime near criticality, the high meta-awareness (i.e., the high precision weighting of second-order likelihoods) implies an intrinsic Riemannian metric of the statistical manifold wherein even very small changes in the parameters imply comparatively large changes in the associated (second-order generative conditional) distribution, *more distinguishable models of the modelling process* reside, per fixed coordinate volume in the statistical manifold, near criticality (see the

mathematical Appendix). Notably – given the common assumption of conscious content mapping to posterior inferences (e.g., Whyte et al., 2024) – this increased intrinsic distinguishability carries over to the posterior. This effectively licenses an additional information-geometric explanation of the frequency of the introspectively experienced cognitive availability of *opacification*, and its associated phenomenology, during advanced meditation: In the computational regime near criticality, there are simply more distinguishable *models of the very process of modelling*.

Local density of distinguishable models

Let (Θ, g) be a d -dimensional Riemannian parameter manifold with volume element

$$d_g(\theta) = \sqrt{\det g(\theta)} d\theta.$$

For small radius $\varepsilon > 0$, the maximal density of ε -distinguishable models per unit coordinate volume at θ scales as

$$\rho_\varepsilon(\theta) \propto \sqrt{\det g(\theta)}.$$

Hence, regions with larger $\det g(\theta)$ admit a higher local density of distinguishable models in parameter space. For more details, see the mathematical Appendix.

Intriguingly, the recent ‘beautiful loop’ theory (Laukkonen et al., 2025) – (a proposal for) a minimal model explanation of phenomenal consciousness – describes phenomenal consciousness as a single systems-level hyper-model of precision-inference and deployment, given the background presence of both a world model (i.e., an *epistemic field*), and *Bayesian binding* (i.e., a competitive access mechanism, similar to the ‘ignition’ that global workspace theory describes). From this perspective, the recursive (global) prediction of precision-weightings across the processing hierarchy (which has here been described in terms of (not-necessarily global) second-order states) captures the inherently reflexive and epistemic nature of phenomenal consciousness (for the phenomenology, see Metzinger, 2024).

Interestingly, the process of construction of these global second-order states itself becomes equipped with a higher precision-weighting (see above) as the systemic dynamics are tuned closer and closer to neuronal criticality. In turn, a more precise likelihood implies a higher information transmission (i.e., mutual information) around this global recursive loop (see the Appendix). Accordingly, neuronal criticality may be interpreted as a dynamical regime of neuronal population dynamics that encodes an increased *epistemic depth* itself.

Strikingly – and counter-intuitively, given the all-too-familiar meta-cognitive knockout many of us experience during the transition from consciousness to its (potential) absence (as in, e.g., anaesthesia or deep sleep) – there are reports of advanced meditators attesting to the possibility to experience a transition from consciousness to unconsciousness in an entirely aware state. These states, in which consciousness itself is said to fully fall away, are meditative endpoints that are sometimes referred to using Pali, the liturgical language of early Buddhism, as *nirodha* and *nirodha sammapatti*. In the scientific literature, these states are referred to as momentary and extended cessations. While these states are reported anecdotally for millennia in contemplative traditions, they have only recently entered neuroscientific discourse (Chowdhury et al., 2023; van Lutterveld et al., 2025, 2025; Yang et al., 2025; for a historical review see Laukkonen et al., 2023). It deserves to be mentioned that this research, while being informed by the attested phenomenology and contemplative doctrine, ultimately draws on these states in the pursuit of scientific knowledge alone.

As described in section 4, an increase in the variance of hierarchically high-level beliefs, mapping onto a relatively liberated bottom-up information flow, is perhaps the single-most central mechanistic parameter corresponding to the induction of advanced meditative states (for a review of computational models of meditation, see (Tal et al., 2025)). This flattening of high level beliefs corresponds neurally to a decreased distance to criticality (see section 3). Indeed, using the active inference modeling framework, research has already begun to sketch the landscape of possibilities of how momentary cessations might arise as a particular meditative endpoint. Specifically, cessations are proposed as the endpoint of further and further increases in the variance of hierarchically high-level beliefs (Laukkonen et al., 2023) or beliefs across the hierarchy as a whole (Prest and Berryman, 2024). Conceptually distinctly, but consistently (see section 4) cessations have been mapped onto an increased entropy (Atad et al., 2025). Consistent with this latter perspective, it deserves to be mentioned that from the perspective of neuronal criticality, a decreased precision-weighting of only relatively high-level beliefs is suggested by the generalized sensitivity to the environment that neuronal criticality affords (see section 4).

Indeed, empirical evidence has shown that starting around 40s before a cessation, large-scale alpha power linearly decreases, being lowest immediately after a cessation (Chowdhury et al., 2023). This is consistent with the proposals that cessations are induced by virtue of attenuated hierarchical processing, as alpha power indexes top-down predictive processing and high-level cognition (Mayer et al., 2016; Klimesch, 2012). Furthermore, regarding neuronal criticality, in a recent EEG study that documented 37 cessation experiences of a single advanced meditator, an analysis of whole-brain detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA) revealed a spike in the DFA-exponent starting 11.3 s before the cessation event, being elevated until 23.6 s post-cessation. This effect was most evident in

the posterior EEG channels and suggests dynamics that are endogenously modulated in the close vicinity of criticality (van Lutterveld et al., 2025). While it may be possible to develop ever-richer models of specific aspects of the phenomenology of advanced meditative states, the radical nature of the “experience” (i.e., its *absence*) in cessation does call for a deeper explanation – potentially even for a new computational-theoretical construct (as noted by (Prest and Berryman, 2024)).

Here, leveraging tools from the field of information geometry, a proposal for such a new computational-theoretical construct is made. Specifically, the limit point of meditative deconstruction (i.e., cessation episodes) – understood in terms of a drastically decreased precision weighting – entails an information-geometric degeneration of the intrinsic (Fisher–Rao) metric of the first-order (generative-conditional) statistical manifold. This implies a vanishing Riemannian volume element: even though the underlying topological structure is still intact, the information-geometric manifold *collapses* metrically to a single point (all points at zero intrinsic distance), implying the vanishing of likelihood-driven information transmission from lower-level observations to inferences at that level (see the mathematical Appendix). Thus, in the limit, posterior belief updating reduces to the prior, and the epistemic value of policies operating over first-order states tends to zero. Put metaphorically: there is nothing to *see*, and nothing to *know*, as the condition of the possibility of knowing itself has been deconstructed.

Notably, the representational grain of the given physical system sets an effective limit, determining for how long belief-updating can be sustained until the (level-specific) minimal difference detection threshold is crossed from above (as likelihood precision is decreased ever further). This level-specific deconstruction of normal (first-order) experience, conjointly expressed with a (functionally implied) increased *epistemic depth* and *meta-awareness* on the second order manifold instantiates (the beginning of) an MPE absorption episode; and explains – together with the increased number of distinct *models of the modeling process* near criticality – phenomenological reports of *clearly* noticing the deconstruction of awareness.

Metric *collapse* of the information-geometric manifold

For the statistical manifold

$$\mathcal{M} = \{ p(\cdot | s, \lambda) : s \in \mathbb{R}^n \}$$

with Fisher–Rao metric (see the mathematical Appendix)

$$I_{ss}(s, \lambda) = \lambda J(s)^\top R^{-1} J(s),$$

as $\lambda \downarrow 0$,

$$I_{ss}(s, \lambda) \longrightarrow 0_{n \times n}, \quad dV(s, \lambda) = \sqrt{\det I_{ss}(s, \lambda)} ds \longrightarrow 0,$$

and, for every small displacement $\Delta s \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(p(\cdot | s + \Delta s, \lambda) \| p(\cdot | s, \lambda)) = \frac{1}{2} \Delta s^\top I_{ss}(s, \lambda) \Delta s + o(\|\Delta s\|^2) \xrightarrow{\lambda \downarrow 0} 0.$$

Hence, all intrinsic (geodesic) distances on \mathcal{M} vanish and the manifold collapses metrically to the one-point limit.

Furthermore, and consistent with the suggestion by (Metzinger and Sandved-Smith, 2024), third order (or $n+1$ th order) meta-attentional layers could, in principle, deconstruct second order (or n th order) layers. The limit of this process would be functionally constituted by a habitually increased ($n+1$ th order) meta-attentional *cognizance* (not presupposing ‘model dependent’ control and associated psychological notions), with *epistemic ignition* having dissolved (as opposed to intentionally transcended (see section 4)) the last remnants of the self-model on that highest order level. From this perspective, neuronal dynamics, endogenously tuned to the most immediate vicinity of criticality, unveil a maximally absorbed non-agentic space of silent epistemicity; hovering in the vicinity of, and inducing, cessations themselves.

‘This is exactly what is so impossible to describe: that it is not an experience at all. This is the first thing that I intuitively realized each time: “This is not an experience now.” [1311]’ (Metzinger, 2024)

6 Conclusion

Neuronal criticality as a framework for the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation offers to constrain the space of possible mappings between phenomenological and mathematical structures. Specifically, based on empirical (and theoretical) knowledge of how informational and dynamical properties vary with the distance to criticality, it is possible to infer how a given phenomenological structure *would* have to transform (by virtue, of, for instance, a specific attentional policy modulating the distance to criticality) *if* the mapping to the mathematical structure were adequate. Neuronal criticality has deep connections to active inference: The flattening of (high-level) beliefs implies, by virtue of increased relaxation times, a smaller distance to criticality (a relationship that has already been deployed in (Carhart-Harris and Friston, 2019)). Furthermore, the neuronal implementation of precision in terms of neuromodulators, and the task-dependent regulation of the distance to criticality by virtue of neuromodulatory control, license a prime candidate as a control parameter for the distance to criticality: Endogenous precision-deployment (i.e., attentional control). After describing specific meditative practices as inducing specific distances to criticality by virtue of differing informational requirements, previous research on advanced meditation was contextualized in terms of the implied distance to criticality. Notably, an increased meta-cognitive awareness is functionally necessary for fast and reliable control of the distance to criticality.

This model offers a new understanding of number of phenomenological properties characteristic of MPE: This comprises aspects such as the phenomenology of *always already*, *incommunicability*, *stillness*, and an increased *epistemicity*; but also an attenuation of the (very last remnants of the) first person perspective in terms of *epistemic ignition*, and a mathematical account of *cessations*. Many of these properties are deeply connected across phenomenological, computational, and neuronal levels of description: Indeed, information-geometrically, comparatively more *models of the process of modeling* are situated in a close-to-critical regime. Notably, and related to a recent proposal for an explanation of phenomenal consciousness in terms of *epistemic depth* (Laukkonen et al., 2025), the dynamical regime of neuronal population dynamics that is endogenously tuned to the close vicinity of criticality functionally implies an increased *epistemic depth*. Thus, in general, neuronal criticality offers a promising framework for the computational neurophenomenology of advanced meditation that is deeply interconnected with previous (active inference) models, while offering new families of empirical and theoretical constraints for further theorizing.

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8 Mathematical Appendix

8.1 Dirichlet Preference Learning and the Epistemic (Pragmatic) Loop

Setup and notation. Discrete time $t \in \mathbb{N}$; horizon $H \in \mathbb{N}$; future indices $\tau = t + 1, \dots, t + H$. Hidden states $s_\tau \in \mathcal{S}$, observations $o_\tau \in \mathcal{O}$ with $|\mathcal{O}| = K$. Policies $\pi \in \Pi$. Predictive beliefs under policy π : $Q(o_\tau, s_\tau | \pi)$ with marginals $Q(o_\tau | \pi)$, $Q(s_\tau | \pi)$, and posterior $Q(s_\tau | o_\tau, \pi)$.

8.1.1 Expected Free Energy (two-term decomposition)

For one-step look-ahead (e.g., (Parr et al., 2022))

$$G_{t+1}(\pi) = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q(o_{t+1}|\pi)}[-\ln P(o_{t+1})]}_{\text{pragmatic (risk)}} - \underbrace{I_Q(s_{t+1}; o_{t+1} | \pi)}_{\text{epistemic (information gain)}}.$$

with mutual information

$$I_Q(s_{t+1}; o_{t+1} | \pi) = \mathbb{E}_{Q(o_{t+1}|\pi)} \left[\text{D}_{\text{KL}}(Q(s_{t+1} | o_{t+1}, \pi) \| Q(s_{t+1} | \pi)) \right].$$

A finite-horizon objective sums (or discounts) over τ :

$$G_t(\pi) = \sum_{\tau=t+1}^{t+H} \left\{ \mathbb{E}_{Q(o_\tau|\pi)}[-\ln P(o_\tau)] - I_Q(s_\tau; o_\tau | \pi) \right\}.$$

Planning-as-inference selects policies via a softmax with policy precision $\gamma > 0$:

$$Q_t(\pi) \propto \exp(-\gamma G_t(\pi)).$$

8.1.2 Prior Preferences over Outcomes as a Dirichlet Belief

Let $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K) \in \Delta^{K-1}$ parameterize preferences over outcomes, with a Dirichlet belief

$$\theta \sim \text{Dir}(\mathbf{c}_t), \quad \mathbf{c}_t = (c_{t,1}, \dots, c_{t,K}) \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^K, \quad c_{0,t} = \mathbb{1}^\top \mathbf{c}_t.$$

Useful expectations are

$$\mathbb{E}[\theta_i \mid \mathbf{c}_t] = \frac{c_{t,i}}{c_{0,t}}, \quad \mathbb{E}[\ln \theta_i \mid \mathbf{c}_t] = \psi(c_{t,i}) - \psi(c_{0,t}),$$

where ψ is the digamma function. A common discrete implementation scores the pragmatic term using the expected log-preference:

$$\mathbb{E}_{Q(o|\pi)}[-\ln P(o)] \approx -\sum_{i=1}^K Q(o=i \mid \pi) \left[\psi(c_{t,i}) - \psi(c_{0,t}) \right].$$

(One may set $P(o=i) = c_{t,i}/c_{0,t}$ and use $-\ln P(o)$; the expression above is a smooth, conjugate surrogate.)

8.1.3 Preference Learning (Pseudo-count Dynamics)

Preference learning generally has been used in active inference before, see, e.g., (Sajid et al., 2021).

Let $\mathbf{e}_{o_t} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ be the one-hot vector for the realized outcome at time t : $(\mathbf{e}_{o_t})_i = \mathbb{1}\{o_t = i\}$. With learning rate $\eta > 0$ and forgetting $\delta \in [0, 1)$, the sample-level update is

$$\mathbf{c}_{t+1} = (1 - \delta) \mathbf{c}_t + \delta \mathbf{c}_{\text{base}} + \eta \mathbf{e}_{o_t}.$$

Before the outcome is realized, the predictive mixture over policies defines the outcome distribution

$$\mathbf{q}_t := \sum_{\pi} Q_t(\pi) Q(o_t = \cdot | \pi) \in \Delta^{K-1},$$

giving the expected update

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{c}_{t+1} | Q_t] = (1 - \delta) \mathbf{c}_t + \delta \mathbf{c}_{\text{base}} + \eta \mathbf{q}_t.$$

Define the mean preference and expected log-preference (“C” vector)

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_t := \frac{\mathbf{c}_t}{c_{0,t}}, \quad \mathbf{C}_t := (C_{t,1}, \dots, C_{t,K}), \quad C_{t,i} = \psi(c_{t,i}) - \psi(c_{0,t}).$$

8.1.4 Closed-loop Recursion

The preceding equations instantiate the loop. For clarity, we list the per-step recursion explicitly:

- (a) $G_{t+1}(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_Q[-\ln P(o_{t+1})] - I_Q(s_{t+1}; o_{t+1} | \pi);$
- (b) $Q_t(\pi) \propto \exp(-\gamma G_t(\pi));$
- (c) $\mathbf{q}_t = \sum_{\pi} Q_t(\pi) Q(o_t = \cdot | \pi);$
- (d) Sample update: $\mathbf{c}_{t+1} = (1 - \delta)\mathbf{c}_t + \delta\mathbf{c}_{\text{base}} + \eta \mathbf{e}_{o_t};$
 Expected update: $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{c}_{t+1} | Q_t] = (1 - \delta)\mathbf{c}_t + \delta\mathbf{c}_{\text{base}} + \eta \mathbf{q}_t;$
- (e) $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{t+1} = \mathbf{c}_{t+1}/c_{0,t+1}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{t+1} = \psi(\mathbf{c}_{t+1}) - \psi(c_{0,t+1}) \mathbb{1}.$

Remark (flattening under diverse sampling). If the outcome frequencies \mathbf{q}_t provide broad coverage, and to the degree that they are uniform, the empirical counts $c_{t,i}$ tend to balance relative to one another. Consequently, the spread of extrinsic values is reduced (since ψ is monotone and $\psi(c_{t,i}) - \psi(c_{t,j}) \rightarrow 0$ as $c_{t,i} \rightarrow c_{t,j}$).

8.2 Minimal Statement (Density \propto Intrinsic Volume Element)

Claim. Let $g(\theta)$ be a Riemannian metric on parameter space $\Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and let $d\text{Vol}_g(\theta) = \sqrt{\det g(\theta)} d\theta$ denote its intrinsic volume element (e.g., (Amari, 2016)). Here, “ ε -distinguishable” means ε -separated in the geodesic distance d_g induced by g , i.e. for any two models $\theta_i \neq \theta_j$, one has $d_g(\theta_i, \theta_j) \geq \varepsilon$. For small radius $\varepsilon > 0$, the maximal density of ε -distinguishable models per unit *coordinate* volume at θ scales as

$$\rho_\varepsilon(\theta) \propto \sqrt{\det g(\theta)}.$$

For fixed small ε , the symbol \propto hides the universal factor ε^{-d} and a dimension-only packing constant, with $O(\varepsilon^2)$ curvature corrections; only the θ -dependence $\sqrt{\det g(\theta)}$ is displayed.

Likelihood geometry (Fisher–Rao). Taking $g(\theta) = I(\theta)$ (Fisher information) gives

$$\rho_\varepsilon(\theta) \propto \sqrt{\det I(\theta)}.$$

Posterior geometry (Laplace, near $\hat{\theta}$). If $\log P(\theta | Y) \approx \text{const} - \frac{1}{2}(\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top H_{\text{post}}(\hat{\theta})(\theta - \hat{\theta})$ on a neighborhood of the MAP $\hat{\theta}$, then locally $g(\theta) = H_{\text{post}}(\hat{\theta})$ (approximately constant), hence

$$\rho_\varepsilon(\hat{\theta}) \propto \sqrt{\det H_{\text{post}}(\hat{\theta})}.$$

Relation to KL- and Euclidean balls (local equivalence). In regular models, the Kullback–Leibler divergence has the quadratic expansion

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P_\theta \| P_{\theta+\delta\theta}) = \frac{1}{2} \delta\theta^\top I(\theta) \delta\theta + o(\|\delta\theta\|^2),$$

and the symmetrized (Jeffreys) divergence equals $\delta\theta^\top I(\theta) \delta\theta + o(\|\delta\theta\|^2)$. Thus, for small radii, KL-balls coincide with geodesic balls of the Fisher–Rao metric up to a constant rescaling of ε . Likewise, in the Laplace case, level sets of $-\log P(\theta | Y)$ are ellipsoids given by $(\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top H_{\text{post}}(\hat{\theta})(\theta - \hat{\theta}) = \text{const}$, i.e. geodesic balls of the metric $g = H_{\text{post}}(\hat{\theta})$ (this Mahalanobis distance is a genuine Riemannian metric, see, e.g., (Pouplin, (2023))) *Consequently*, “larger information/precision \Rightarrow larger $\sqrt{\det g} \Rightarrow$ higher local density of distinguishable models per unit *coordinate* volume” holds in both geometries.

8.3 Likelihood–Intrinsic–Metric Collapse \Rightarrow No Posterior Update

Notation. Hidden state $s \in \mathbb{R}^n$, observation $o \in \mathbb{R}^m$. Generative mean $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is twice continuously differentiable. Jacobian $J(s) := \partial g(s) / \partial s \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. Prediction error $\varepsilon(s) := o - g(s)$. Identity I_m for $m \times m$. Unless otherwise stated, all expectations $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ in Section 8.3 are with respect to $o \mid s, \lambda$ under the likelihood.

Nonlinear Gaussian likelihood with fixed noise shape:

$$p(o \mid s, \lambda) = \mathcal{N}(g(s), \lambda^{-1}R), \quad R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m} \text{ fixed, } R \succ 0, \lambda > 0.$$

Noise independence: $\varepsilon = o - g(s)$ is independent of s with covariance $\text{Cov}(\varepsilon) = \lambda^{-1}R$.

Regularity: $g \in C^2$ on a neighborhood of interest; moments finite so that differentiation under the integral is valid.

From Log-likelihood to the Intrinsic Fisher Information Metric

Log-likelihood and score

Up to constants independent of s ,

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(s, \lambda; o) &= \frac{1}{2} \log \det(\lambda R^{-1}) - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon(s)^\top (\lambda R^{-1}) \varepsilon(s) \\ &= \frac{m}{2} \log \lambda - \frac{\lambda}{2} \varepsilon(s)^\top R^{-1} \varepsilon(s). \end{aligned}$$

Using $\partial_s \varepsilon(s) = -J(s)$ and the identity $\partial_s [\varepsilon^\top A \varepsilon] = 2(\partial_s \varepsilon)^\top A \varepsilon$ for constant A ,

$$\nabla_s \ell(s, \lambda; o) = -\frac{\lambda}{2} \partial_s [\varepsilon^\top R^{-1} \varepsilon] = \lambda J(s)^\top R^{-1} \varepsilon(s).$$

The score above is the predictive-coding update signal: a *precision-weighted* back-propagated prediction error.

Fisher information metric in s (outer-product and curvature forms)

Lemma 1 (Fisher information metric). *The Fisher information in s (the intrinsic Riemannian metric on the statistical manifold $\mathcal{M} = \{p(\cdot | s, \lambda) : s \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$) is*

$$I_{ss}(s, \lambda) = \mathbb{E}[\nabla_s \ell \nabla_s \ell^\top] = \lambda J(s)^\top R^{-1} J(s).$$

Proof. From the score expression,

$$\mathbb{E}[\nabla_s \ell \nabla_s \ell^\top] = \lambda^2 J^\top R^{-1} \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon \varepsilon^\top] R^{-1} J = \lambda^2 J^\top R^{-1} (\lambda^{-1} R) R^{-1} J = \lambda J^\top R^{-1} J.$$

Intrinsic-metric collapse and local KL/geodesic indistinguishability

As $\lambda \downarrow 0$, the intrinsic metric collapses:

$$I_{ss}(s, \lambda) \longrightarrow 0_{n \times n}.$$

Geometrically, the Riemannian lengths of tangent vectors vanish and the manifold of likelihoods loses local resolving power in the s -direction. Equivalently, for a small displacement Δs ,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(p(\cdot | s + \Delta s, \lambda) || p(\cdot | s, \lambda)) = \frac{1}{2} \Delta s^\top I_{ss}(s, \lambda) \Delta s + o(\|\Delta s\|^2) \xrightarrow{\lambda \downarrow 0} 0,$$

so (to second order) both local KL and the induced squared geodesic length between nearby likelihoods collapse with λ .

Implications: Posterior Update and Epistemic Value

Posterior update collapses as the metric collapses

Let the prior be $p(s) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_0, \Sigma_0)$. Perform a single Laplace/EKF linearization at an expansion point \bar{s} :

$$g(s) \approx g(\bar{s}) + J(\bar{s})(s - \bar{s}).$$

Define the linearized observation $y := o - g(\bar{s})$ and $\delta := s - \bar{s}$. Then $y \mid \delta \sim \mathcal{N}(J\delta, \lambda^{-1}R)$ and $\delta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\delta, \Sigma_0)$ with $\mu_\delta = \mu_0 - \bar{s}$. Standard Gaussian conditioning (e.g., see Bishop (2006)) yields

$$\Sigma_{\text{post}}^{-1} = \Sigma_0^{-1} + \underbrace{\lambda J(\bar{s})^\top R^{-1} J(\bar{s})}_{I_{ss}(\bar{s}, \lambda)},$$

$$\mu_{\text{post}} = \mu_0 + \Sigma_{\text{post}} \lambda J(\bar{s})^\top R^{-1} (o - g(\bar{s}) - J(\bar{s})(\mu_0 - \bar{s})).$$

In particular, for the common choice $\bar{s} = \mu_0$, this reduces to

$$\mu_{\text{post}} = \mu_0 + \Sigma_{\text{post}} \lambda J(\mu_0)^\top R^{-1} (o - g(\mu_0)).$$

Proposition 1 (Metric collapse \Rightarrow no posterior update). *As $\lambda \downarrow 0$, $\Sigma_{\text{post}} \rightarrow \Sigma_0$ and $\mu_{\text{post}} \rightarrow \mu_0$; i.e. the posterior equals the prior (no likelihood-driven update).*

Proof. Immediate from the posterior covariance and mean formulas and the Fisher information identity: the information increment equals the intrinsic metric $I_{ss}(\bar{s}, \lambda) = \lambda J^\top R^{-1} J \rightarrow 0$, and the mean update is proportional to λ . Equivalently, at the gradient level $\nabla_s \ell = \lambda J^\top R^{-1} \varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. \square

Epistemic value (mutual information) vanishes with the metric

Under the local linear-Gaussian model above with Gaussian prior $s \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_0, \Sigma_0)$, the (expected) information gain between prior and posterior is the mutual information (e.g., Cover and Thomas, 2006)

$$I(S; O) = H(S) - H(S \mid O) = \frac{1}{2} \log \det(\Sigma_0 \Sigma_{\text{post}}^{-1}).$$

Using the expression for $\Sigma_{\text{post}}^{-1}$,

$$I(S; O) \approx \frac{1}{2} \log \det\left(I_n + \Sigma_0 I_{ss}(\bar{s}, \lambda)\right) = \frac{1}{2} \log \det\left(I_n + \lambda \Sigma_0 J(\bar{s})^\top R^{-1} J(\bar{s})\right).$$

Thus, as $\lambda \downarrow 0$, $I(S; O) \rightarrow 0$